

Synthesis of porous hollow spheres using aqueous metal ammonium carbonate complex solution as novel precursor for energy storage application

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We have developed two simple synthetic strategies for variety of metal oxide/sulfide/carbide and corresponding carbon/rGO incorporated hollow spheres. Different carbon incorporated nanocomposite hollow spheres have been realized using corresponding aqueous metal ammonium carbonate complex solution as precursor, thiourea as sulfur source and combined sucrose-CTAB as simple soft template as well as carbon source through hydrothermal treatment followed by calcination (1-2). In another strategy, pristine and rGO incorporated hollow spheres have also been synthesized through as simple spray-drying based strategy using the identical metal and sulfur precursor without any organic additives (3-4). Synthesized hollow spheres exhibit superior energy storage material as anode in LIB/ECC or active catalyst for H₂ generation through electrochemical water splitting. As for example, TiO₂-rGO (20%) hollow sphere showed exceptionally high capacity of 274 mA h g⁻¹ at 18.8 mA g⁻¹.

References

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